

**THERAPEUTIC EFFICACY OF AN AYURVEDIC FORMULARY PREPARATION IN
EKAKUSTHA (ERYTHRODERMIC PSORIASIS): A CLINICAL CASE STUDY*****¹Dr. Tulasidas Pandiri MD, ²Dr. Rajani Pydi MD**¹Associate Professor, Department of Swasthavritta, ²Professor, Department of Kaumarabhritya,
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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda holds a unique position among life sciences for its effective treatment of various skin disorders, offering lasting therapeutic effects since ancient times. In Ayurveda, significant skin diseases are categorized under the classification of Kushta, with Ekakushta being one of them. The classical texts of Ayurveda recognize each type of Kushta as a manifestation of Tridosha, identifying Ekakushta as a Vatakapha condition. Factors such as mental stress, negative emotions, disrespect towards teachers, and engagement in sinful activities contribute to its development. The characteristics of Ekakushta include aswedam (lack of perspiration), mahavastum (extensive), matsyashakalopam (similar to fish scales), and krishnaruna (blackish red color). The disease described in Ayurveda closely resembles psoriasis, which is an immune-mediated inflammatory condition characterized by intermittent flare-ups and remissions. Psoriasis is defined by the presence of erythematous, scaly plaques, particularly affecting the extensor surfaces. A 50-year-old male patient visited the outpatient department with complaints of itchy, scaly, black lesions on his body for the past six years. He was diagnosed with Ekakustha (Erythrodermic Psoriasis). The patient underwent Sodhana therapy followed by Samana treatment, resulting in the resolution of all symptoms within two months. Patients with psoriasis can benefit from Ayurvedic treatment.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Ekakustha, Psoriasis, Erythrodermic Psoriasis, PASI Score.**INTRODUCTION**

The skin is the largest organ of the body and serves as the primary barrier against pathogens. Skin diseases can lead to physical, psychological, emotional, and social embarrassment. On average, 10-15% of general practitioners deal with skin disorders, making it the second most common cause of work absenteeism in the private sector.^[1]

With modernization and westernization, junk food, soft drinks, alcohol, irregular work shifts, and non-vegetarian food have become integral to daily life. Additionally, factors such as unhealthy dietary practices (like consuming milk with sour fruits or fermented products) and lifestyle choices (such as using air conditioning, daytime sleeping, and suppressing natural urges) contribute to low immunity and various comorbidities. Among these, "Kushta" is a frequently encountered condition.^[2]

In Ayurveda, all skin diseases fall under the category of Kushtha, which is further divided into Mahakushtha and Kshudrakushtha. Ayurvedic texts indicate that all Kushtas involve iridocyclitis, but the type of Kushtha is determined by the predominance of specific doshas. Among these types, "Ekakushtha" is considered particularly distressing.^[3]

Modern medicine describes leprosy using the "4 D's": Discomfort, Disability, Disfigurement, and Death. In the case of psoriasis, the first three D's are observed.^[4] Ayurvedic texts do not provide a direct equivalent to modern psoriasis, but conditions such as "Kitibha," "Charmadala," and "Ekakushtha" are often compared to it. Psoriasis is a chronic, non-infectious inflammatory autoimmune disease characterized by well-defined red plaques covered with silvery scales.^[5]

The disease Kitibha does not exhibit scaling but may show discoloration and rough texture.^[6] In contrast, Charmadala is characterized by swelling and scaling.^[7] However, psoriasis is typically painless and is sometimes referred to as "the healthy man's disease." Ekakushtha includes symptoms such as Aswedana, Mahavasthu, Matsya shakalopam, and Krishnaruna vranavastha, which can be likened to psoriasis, making it a relevant comparison in this case study. Acharya Charak has noted the involvement of Vata and Kapha doshas in Ekakushtha.^[8]

Psoriasis is one of the most fascinating and complex skin disorders. It is known for being chronic and is characterized by periods of remission and flare-ups. The condition often runs in families and can be triggered by factors such as climate and Streptococcal infections. Psoriasis primarily involves issues with keratinization. Both men and women are equally susceptible, and it can affect individuals of all ages. Psychological stress is highlighted as a significant factor that can worsen the disease.^[9]

Modern medical treatments for psoriasis include PUVA (photochemotherapy and ultraviolet radiation) and corticosteroids.^[10] However, these treatments can lead to serious side effects, such as liver and kidney failure and bone marrow depletion.^[11] Therefore, there is a pressing need to discover safe and effective treatments for psoriasis, and this is where Ayurveda plays a crucial role.

Table 1: PASI score of the patient before trail.

	Head & neck	Upper limbs	Trunk	Lower limbs	Total
Erythema	2	2	3	1	
Induration	3	2	3	2	
Scaling	3	2	3	2	
Area score	3	2	3	1	
Total	11	8	12	6	37

METHODS

Treatment Plan: In Ayurveda, the condition known as Ekakushtha is treated using both internal (Antah Parimarjana Chikitsa) and external (Bahir Parimarjana Chikitsa) therapies. Given the nature of the disease, which is prone to remissions and exacerbations, it is essential to manage it through Shodhana, followed by Shamanoushadhis and Twaklepa.

The following treatment methods will be implemented

- Shodhana chikitsa
- Samana chikitsa
- Stress management
- Pathya ahara (appropriate diet)
- Lifestyle changes

SELECTION OF DRUG

According to Charaka, any substance that alleviates a patient's ailments can be classified as Aushadhi.^[14] Therefore, careful consideration is necessary when choosing a medication. To achieve the desired

The distinctive treatment approach of Ayurveda offers long-lasting results and improves patients' quality of life through its three fundamental principles: Shodhana, Shamana, and Nidana parivarjana.^[12]

Considering the before mentioned causes and recognizing psoriasis as an autoimmune disorder with psychosomatic implications, a combined treatment of Darvyadhi lepa^[13] (an external application) and Kustahara yoga (an internal drug formulated by me) is recommended for this case.

CASE REPORT

A 50-year-old male patient presented at the outpatient department with the main complaint of dark scaly plaques covering his body for the past six years. Associated with itchy, scaly lesions initially appeared on his chest and gradually spread to his entire body over this period. The itching worsened with the consumption of non-vegetarian food and particularly during the winter months, but there were no associated symptoms of fever or arthritis. The patient has a five-year history of diabetes, which is managed with allopathic medications and is currently under control. Despite having taken allopathic treatments and even steroids for his skin condition, he experienced no relief. He also reported irregular bowel habits, a normal appetite, disturbed sleep and a sedentary lifestyle due to his work. There is no family history of diabetes, hypertension, tuberculosis, cancer, or other comorbidities.

therapeutic concentration of a drug at its site of action, a large quantity may need to be administered, which can lead to gastric discomfort and unwanted side effects.^[15] Even if a drug is relatively safe, frequent dosing is often impractical today. Given this context, it can be concluded that solely relying on oral administration is insufficient for disease management. Thus, local application becomes a crucial aspect in treating Kushtha, as it delivers the highest concentration of the drug directly to the site of action, can be used more frequently, and does not disrupt the gastric environment. In this study, Kustahara yoga has been formulated for oral administration, while Darvyadhi lepa^[16] has been chosen for local application.

Kustahara yoga: (internal use)

Ingredients: The following drugs should be taken in equal quantities

1. Khadira
2. Harithaki
3. Aragwadha
4. Vidanga

5. Haridra
6. Indrayava
7. Nimba
8. Guduchi
9. Yastimadhu
10. Jatamamsi

Darvyadhi lepa: (external application)

Ingredients

1. Daruharidra

2. Gomutra

Churna of Daruharidra bhavana done with Gomutra as per classics.^[17]

Treatment advised

Drug	Dose	Duration	Anupana
<i>Erandabrista Harithaki</i> for <i>Kostha sodhana</i>	3gms *HS	3days	Luke warm water
<i>Kusthahara yoga</i> for internal use	5gms *BD	2 months	Luke warm water
<i>Daryadi lepa</i> for external application	QS *BD	2 months	-

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: PASI score of the patient after trail.

	Head & neck	Upper limbs	Trunk	Lower limbs	Total
Erythema	0	1	1	1	
Induration	1	0	1	0	
Scaling	0	0	0	0	
Area score	1	1	1	1	
Total	2	3	3	2	9

Erandabrista Haritaki churna given to the patient for mridhu sodhana of Kosta. It passifies the pitta dosha of the body and helps in proper absorption of dravyas.^[18]

In the above mentioned Kusthahara yoga, Khadira, Harithaki, Aragwadha, Vidanga, Haridra are taken from Kushtahara dasaimani, Indrayava is kandugna and tridosha samaka, and Khadira is antiviral, antifungal. Harithaki, Aragwadha, Haridra is antimicrobial, antibacterial, antifungal, antihelminthic, antiparasitic. Khadira, Aragwadha are also having antiviral property. Nimba is pittakapha samaka and kandugna, and natural immune booster, natural steroid, antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, antiinflammatory,^[19] Guduchi is tridosha samaka, medhya and immunomodulator, tranquilizer, antiseptic in nature^[20], Indrayava is antimicrobial, anti histamic. Yastimadhu is medhya, having steroidal effect and is a stress buster, anti-inflammatory. Jathamamsi is tridosha samaka, medhya and acts as a tranquilizer, stress buster, antidepressant.^[21] Because of the above properties these ten drugs are selected and formulated and named as Kusthahara yoga.

Daruharidra is kapha pitta samaka, varnya, and having anti-inflammatory effect, local anesthetic, antiparasitic, antibacterial, antiinflammatory.^[22] Gomutra is vata kapha samaka, kandu hara.^[23] These drugs are taken for clinical study. Darvyadilepa is Gomutra bhavita Drauharidra is Pittasamaka, Rakta Shodhaka, Swedajanana and Varnya, anaesthetic, antiprotozoal.^[24] Gomutra ia antibacterial, antiinflammatory, antifungal, antimicrobial and because of theekshna, ksharayukta it does lekhana which helps in treating skin diseases.^[25]

The patient used these medications for two months and experienced significant improvement in itching, scaling, and the spread of skin issues [Fig 2]. The PASI score indicated significant change before and after

treatment^[26,27] [Table 2] and it was reduced from 37 to 9. Following a mild detoxification, the patient felt lighter, and bowel movements became regular. Within a week of using both internal and external medications, 80% of the itching ceased, and the dark psoriatic patches began to change color and became less widespread. After 20 days, the scaling of the skin gradually stopped, and by the end of the second month treatment, the patches nearly disappeared, lot of change in itching and scaling, and the skin returned to its normal color, allowing for sweating.

Recommendations

Diet: The patient was advised to avoid sour and spicy food, junk food, fried items, and fermented foods. **Lifestyle:** The patient should engage in 30 minutes of walking daily, along with regular practice of pranayama and meditation.

CONCLUSION

Ekakustha (Psoriasis) is classified as a Kastasadhya condition. Considering the psychosomatic and autoimmune aspects of the disease, a treatment plan was developed. Through the process of mridhusodhana, the aggravated pitta dosha was eliminated from the body, which improved the drug's absorption rate. The medications chosen for Kusthahara yoga primarily targeted the symptoms of itching and inflammation while possessing properties to alleviate vata and kapha enhance strength, thereby addressing the psychosomatic and autoimmune characteristics of the disease. The patient experienced significant relief in a short period, indicating the effectiveness of this treatment approach. Darvyadi lepa is a classical remedy, proved to be particularly effective on psoriatic patches as it was prepared in-house rather than purchased commercially. Additionally, dietary and lifestyle modifications played a crucial role in the management of the condition. The patient adhered strictly to the prescribed diet and lifestyle during

treatment and was closely monitored. They practiced pranayama techniques puraka, kumbhaka, and rechaka for at least 15 minutes daily, along with 15 minutes of meditation and a minimum of 30 minutes of walking each day, which contributed to patient psychological and physical well-being. These activities enhanced the drug's absorption rate and facilitated quicker symptom

remission. This study suggests that Ayurveda offers hope for managing autoimmune and psychosomatic diseases that are often challenging to treat. Although this is a single case study, it serves as a foundation for further research involving a larger number of cases in this area of the disease.

Fig 1: (Before Treatment).

Fig 2: (After Treatment).

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